

METHODS OF FORMATION OF LANGUAGE SKILLS IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotation: Currently, the methods of teaching foreign languages are improving. Especially intensive methods, that is modern methods, play an important role in the rapid growth of language in the learner layer.

Keywords: teaching languages, educational process, the methodology, Audiolingual method, logical memory, podcasts, the fluency and purity in speech.

At present, a lot of work is being done not only on the teaching of foreign languages, but also on finding new methods of teaching all subjects and testing them in practice. This is one of the most important issues that needs to be addressed in order to improve the current educational process and expand the scope of knowledge. If we look only at a foreign language, it should be noted that if earlier teaching a foreign language was considered a study of the language system, in later years the most important goal of teaching was to increase the student's speech in a foreign language. Therefore, the methodology for the formation of language skills is associated with changes in linguistics, as well as psychology, and the social development of society. Take the Audiolingual method for example. The emergence of this method was influenced by changes in the science of linguistics, that is the structural flow. It includes the following factors:

- Start teaching a foreign language by teaching oral speech;
- Carrying out language learning on the basis of various structures, patterns of speech;
- Repeat language materials based on exercises;
- The choice of grammatical patterns and vocabulary, the results of comparing a foreign language with the native language;
- Great attention to pronunciation.

Of course, this method also has its drawbacks. For example, the abundance of mechanical exercises and the lack of real speech exercises are

clear examples of this. The use of lexical material on the basis of a certain grammatical structure contributes to the formation of this methodological mechanism. That is, it has an effective effect at the initial stage. In this case, students are demanded to know well present tenses, past tenses, future tenses.

Past continuous, past perfect, future perfect in the past stages increase the opportunities for personal development of the student and the formation of his worldview. It is also important to have assignments that develop logical memory. Because at this stage, the student accumulates a lot of material that needs to be memorized. Reading, translating, listening to and mastering various podcasts, and organizing more dialogues are important aspects of the methodology. Teaching students to think in classrooms and to tell any facts about language is a very effective way. In this process, assignments can also be in Uzbek. Because those who are just learning a foreign language may find it difficult to accept assignments. That is, translation can be a bit difficult. These include a variety of games, listening to small texts, creative role-playing games, interesting questions and answers, speaking, listening, writing, reading skills assignments and exhibitions. It is known that in teaching a foreign language it is advisable to organize the learning process taking into account the age characteristics of the learners. The most important thing here is that the task set for the student should be in accordance with their abilities, that is, it should not be too difficult for the student.

At present, special subjects and textbooks have been developed for students to develop language skills in higher education institutions. In particular, in the subject "Integration of language skills" students are taught in four skills. So these are: reading, writing, listening and speaking skills. Given that English is largely based on the above 4 skills, there is a separate teaching methodology for each. However, it should not be forgotten that these skills are closely related to each other. For example, cannot omit the listening part while developing speaking, because in order to speak, one must first listen, in order to develop the ability to listen, one must experiment with speaking more. Or take a reading part with a writing part. Both are inextricably linked. The reason is that you can not write without reading, you can not read without mastering writing. To be more precise, all four language skills complement each other. If the position is lacking in

any skill, the fluency and purity of speech will be compromised. As a result, we may be misinforming the people around us.

The formation of language skills largely depends on practice. That is, the more the student works on himself and learns each stage with patience and quality, depending on his level, the more his language skills will develop. As mentioned above, it is important for every learner to know his or her level. This means that there are several stages in the process of learning a language and you have to master them step by step. More precisely, someone is at the level of beginner, someone at the level of intermediate, pre intermediate, upper intermediate and so on. It is impossible to pass from one level to another without mastering it perfectly. If your intermediate level is at the intermediate level and you use upper intermediate level textbooks in the process of language learning, the knowledge you are acquiring will be confused and incomprehensible. As a result, it strains your brain beyond accepting knowledge and skills that are beyond its scope, and at the same time creates a shallowness in the knowledge of the old normal level. That is why it is advisable for students to use books and textbooks at a level that suits them. The ability to speak confidently and fluently is something which children will develop during their time at school. And something that will help them throughout their life. Speaking is interactive process where information is shaved and if necessarily, acted upon by the listener. So, it's important to develop both Speaking and listening skills in order to communicate effectively.

Every day, we write, whether it's a school paper, blog post, work document, email or social media update. Your writing represents who you are personally and professionally, so it's worth it to hone your skills. Here are some writing skills and writing tips to help you communicate better in text:

1. Set writing goals
2. Writing in the morning
3. Write daily
4. Get inspired by the research
5. Experiment with writing prompts
6. Outline
7. Keep it brief
8. Use active voice
9. Don't Email angry

10. Write like you talk, within reason.

Today, learning language is becoming a vital necessity. Therefore the demand for language learning is growing. Especially, since English is recognized as a global language, it is studied in almost all countries of the world. There is a great need for this language, especially in our country. A number of textbooks and collections have been created for Uzbek youth to master the English language, which will be briefly discussed below. First of all, it is important to choose the right textbooks. Then they are taught in order according to the age and potential of each learner. The article discusses some methods of teaching foreign languages skills. A brief description of the difficulties that learners face in mastering English and their solutions. Learning language has become one of the most pressing requirements of today. Because this is the demand of the time: that is following the methods of the leading countries in the socio-political and other spheres, we are also among the leaders. The demand for learning language in Uzbekistan is very high. In particular the English language is evolving from year to year. Different types of textbooks and manuals are published depending on the age and level of kindergarten, school, university and other learners. Now we introduce you with listening skills. Listening is the ability to accurately receive and interpret messages in the communication process. Listening is key to all effective communication. Without the ability to listen effectively, messages are easily misunderstood. As a result, communication breaks down and the sender of the message can easily become frustrated or irritated. If there is on communication skills you should aim to aim to master, then listening is it. Listening is so important that many top employers provide listening skills training for their employees. This is not surprising when you consider that good listening skills can lead to better customer satisfaction, greater productivity with fewer mistakes, and increased sharing of information that in turn can lead to more creative and innovative work. Many successful leaders and entrepreneurs credit their success to effective listening skills. Richard Branson frequently quotes listening as one of the main factors behind the success of Virginia. Effective listening is a skill that underpins all positive human relationships. Spend some time thinking about and developing your listening skills - they are the building blocks of success. The purpose of listening: There is no doubt that effective listening is an extremely important life skill. Why is listening so important? Listening

serves a number of possible purposes, and the purpose of listening will depend on the situation and the nature of the communication.

1. To specifically focus on the messages being communicated, avoiding distractions and preconceptions.
2. To gain a full and accurate understanding into the speakers point of view and ideas.
3. To critically assess what is being said.
4. To observe the non-verbal signals accompanying what is being said to enhance understanding.

Vocabulary:

To develop our speaking skills, we first need to know the right words. Vocabulary development begins when are infants, as we learn to describe the world around us and communicate our needs. This progresses from single word to sentence when children are 2 or 3, at which point they will normally have a vocabulary of 150- 300 words. Vocabulary development is where students understand the meanings and pronunciations of words necessary for communication. When they understand what a word means, they can check what the word or sentence means. This is so important so they can check the what the word or sentence means and they can keep up a conversation. If they understand what the other person is saying and they know what vocabulary to say back, they are halfway there to communicating effectively. Did you know that to be considered fluent in a language, you need to have a vocabulary of around 10,000 words?

Grammar:

You may think that grammar is something we only need for written language. But grammar includes lots of important areas for spoken language such as an understanding of tenses and understanding of tenses and the correct way to structure sentences. Grammar helps us to convey information in a way that the listener will recognize and understand.

Pronunciation:

Understanding how to correctly pronounce words is another important element of speaking skills. We learn how to pronounce words by listening to those around us, such as our parents, friends and teachers. Pronunciation varies from country to country, and even city to city! A lot of this comes from phonemic awareness. This involves understanding the small units that make up spoken language. English can differ from quite a lot compared to other languages. Some phenomena might not be in ESL

students native languages and children's minds are trained to categories phonemes in their first language, so it can become confusing. Developing this ability in English can come from playing language games and using songs and poems to reiterate rhythm and repetitions. Phonics us where students start to see relationships between the sound of spoken language and graphics which are the letters and spelling repetition sounds in written language

Fluency:

Fluency in spoken language is something that naturally develops as children go through school, as they are using and practicing speaking skills every day. Reading widely is a good way to improve fluency as it introduces children to new vocabulary and reinforces their knowledge of spoken language. Fluency is the ability to hear words and understand them straight away. If they see a word written down, they can read it aloud and pronounce it properly. Ways to develop this include guiding your students to read passages out loud . You could also get your students to read a loud . You could also get your students to read aloud in front of the class. This builds their confidence and also helps them to annunciate better. The more fluent your students are in English, the more interesting, exciting and insightful conversations they can have.

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